

Preview of Award 0618885 - Annual Project Report

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Cover

Federal Agency and Organization Element to Which Report is Submitted:	4900
Federal Grant or Other Identifying Number Assigned by Agency:	0618885
Project Title:	Providing Organizational Support to the U.S. Arctic Science Program
PD/PI Name:	Helen V Wiggins, Principal Investigator
Recipient Organization:	Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.
Project/Grant Period:	03/15/2008 - 04/30/2014
Reporting Period:	03/01/2013 - 02/28/2014
Submitting Official (if other than PD\PI):	Helen V Wiggins Principal Investigator
Submission Date:	04/02/2014
Signature of Submitting Official (signature shall be submitted in accordance with agency specific instructions)	Helen V Wiggins

Accomplishments

* What are the major goals of the project?

The overall goal of the project is to provide organizational support to the NSF Arctic Sciences Section, Division of Polar Programs to develop, promote, and implement arctic research and education activities.

* What was accomplished under these goals (you must provide information for at least one of the 4 categories below)?

Major Activities: Major activities included:

- Arctic Community Science Planning** – coordinating science planning for the arctic research community across disciplinary and organizational boundaries; includes Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) Coordination and the Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC) tasks.
- Coordination Support for NSF Division of Arctic Sciences Programs** – coordination and support for the Division of Arctic Sciences programs; includes Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program Coordination, Arctic

Natural Science Program Coordination, Arctic Social Sciences Program Coordination, Arctic Section Science Materials, NSF's Forum of Arctic Research Operators (FARO) dues, and Research Support and Logistics workshop planning.

- **Arctic Science Education** – development and coordination of arctic-focused educational activities; includes various Arctic Science Education Activities and the Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series.
- **Information and Outreach** – information and outreach activities; includes *Witness the Arctic* newsletter, Website and Internet Resources, ArcticInfo mailing list, Directory of Arctic Researchers, Internet Media Archive, and Arctic Community Outreach.

Specific Objectives: Two key objectives cross all activities funded under this Cooperative Agreement:

- Provide tools and activities to link knowledge and people across arctic research disciplines, institutions, contexts, and scales.
- Broaden participation of arctic scientists and educators, including early career scientists and stakeholders, in arctic research efforts.

Significant Results: Since the activities funded in this product are not research activities, 'results' are interpreted as outcomes and achievements, and are reported below.

Key outcomes or Other achievements: Key outcomes or achievements in 2013 included:

- **Sea Ice Outlook (SIO)** - Development of online reports that provide a syntheses and projections of the arctic sea ice minimum throughout the summer. ARCUS worked with the lead editor (James Overland, NOAA) and dozens of contributing groups to develop, edit, organize, publish, and distribute the monthly online reports, which included full pan-arctic and regional reports and executive summaries. The 2013 Outlook reports are archived at: <http://www.arcus.org/search-program/seaiceoutlook>
- **Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook (SIWO)** - Provides weekly ice forecasts for the Northern Bering Sea and southern Chukchi Sea regions of Alaska during walrus hunting season. The SIWO is a collaboration between ARCUS and the University of Alaska Fairbanks, the Eskimo Walrus Commission, the National Weather Service, and the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration. Local observers from Alaskan communities provide observations on sea ice and weather conditions, which are combined with ice and wind forecasts from the National Weather Service. The 2013 weekly SIWO reports are archived at: <http://www.arcus.org/search-program/siwo>
- **Report on US Arctic Observing Coordination** - ARCUS worked with a workshop Organizing Committee to develop a final workshop report on US Arctic Observing Coordination. The report included descriptions of 11 "showcase projects" that would demonstrate effective approaches towards interagency collaboration for the AON. The report also summarized recommendations on data management, challenges for building a coordinated network, and future directions and opportunities. The report is available at: <http://www.arcus.org/search->

program/aon

- **SEARCH Strategic Planning** - ARCUS worked with the SEARCH Science Steering Committee (SSC: <http://www.arcus.org/search-program/sciencecoordination/ssc-committee>), with input from the broader research community, to finalize a new governance structure to implement a new vision and mission for SEARCH. The final governance structure was developed from monthly SSC teleconferences, which ARCUS organized and facilitated; targeted teleconferences; conversations and teleconferences with members of the SEARCH Observing Change Panel (<http://www.arcus.org/search-program/sciencecoordination/observing>); a small in person meeting (at the 2013 Fall AGU Meeting); and a significant amount of review and work via email. A document describing the framework was posted on the SEARCH website. ARCUS also provided administrative, logistical, and travel support for the SEARCH Science Steering Committee chair and Committee members.
- **Arctic Observing Network Discussions** - Worked with the NSF AON Program Director to launch and manage a process whereby arctic researchers or stakeholders can receive funding for telecommunications assistance, meeting room rental, and professional facilitation to lead discussions related to issues concerning the review, management, communication, and connectivity of long-term observing: <http://www.arcus.org/search-program/aon/discussion-funding-form>. ARCUS staff participated and provided staff support at the Arctic Observing Summit conference (<http://www.arcticobservingsummit.org/aos-2013>).
- **Support for the Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC) Secretariat** - Provided Salary, travel, and some administrative support for the IARPC Executive Secretary and Implementation Scientist.
- **Initial Development of IARPC Website** - ARCUS worked closely with IARPC staff to determine initial needs and a plan for developing a new website focused on IARPC implementation activities. ARCUS contracted with a web development firm, Webitects, Inc., who completed a user research phase in collaboration with ARCUS, IARPC staff, and participants of IARPC activities.
- **Arctic Research Logistics Workshop** - ARCUS organized a workshop in collaboration with NSF and a workshop Organizing Committee 7-9 October 2013 in Arlington, Virginia. The workshop was held to discuss strategies and recommendations for future Arctic research support and logistics. Sixty-two participants attended from a diverse range of disciplines and perspectives. The goal of the discussions was to develop a suite of specific, actionable steps for developing logistics support to best serve Arctic science over the next decade. A community survey was circulated to solicit broad input on pertinent topics before the workshop. The final workshop agenda, participant list, plenary presentations, and background information, can be found through the workshop website at: <http://www.arcus.org/logistics/2013-workshop>. ARCUS worked with the Organizing Committee to develop an initial outline of the workshop recommendations, which was circulated to all workshop participants. The final report is expected in Spring 2014.
- **Arctic Visiting Speakers (AVS)** - The AVS program provides small travel grants for experts to travel to communities and audiences to share knowledge on the Arctic. In 2013, AVS supported seven tours on a range of

arctic science topics and audiences. The estimated number of audience members for 2013 is 4,584, including K-12 students, college students, and the general public. Information on the 2013 tours can be found at: <http://www.arcus.org/arctic-visiting-speakers>

- **AGU Community Meeting Room** - ARCUS organized use of two "open-use" meeting rooms at the 2013 Fall Meeting of the American Geophysical Union. The rooms encouraged scientific collaboration and made face-to-face meetings of opportunity possible for the arctic research community. Thirty-six groups met in the rooms, with over 400 participants. A list of community meetings held is available at: <http://www.arcus.org/communitymeetings/agu/2013>
- **Witness the Arctic Newsletter** - *Witness the Arctic* is an online newsletter that provides information on current arctic research efforts and findings, significant research initiatives, national policy affecting arctic research, international activities, and profiles of arctic institutions. In 2013, ARCUS published three issues on schedule. The 2013 issues (Volume 17, Numbers 1-3) are available online at: <http://www.arcus.org/witness-the-arctic/2013/1> . Once published, Witness the Arctic newsletter is distributed through the Witness the Arctic mailing list (with over 6,800 subscribers), and is also announced via the ARCUS website and other mailing lists.
- **ArcticInfo Email List** - ARCUS maintained and managed ArcticInfo, the primary electronic mailing list for the arctic research community. ArcticInfo provides timely information about funding opportunities, important events, publications, position announcements, and other news. All postings are archived in a searchable directory on the ARCUS website (<http://www.arcus.org/arctic-info>). In 2013, there were 370 announcements and 7,000 subscribers.
- **Directory of Arctic Researchers** - Maintained the Directory of Arctic Researchers, which includes information on over 4,100 U.S. and international arctic researchers. The Directory facilitates networking and collaboration in arctic research and education efforts between individual investigators, institutions, funding agencies, and arctic stakeholders: <http://www.arcus.org/researchers>.
- **Arctic Calendar** - An up-to-date and calendar of arctic meetings and events: <http://calendar.arcus.org/>
- **Arctic Forum** - Provided partial staff time for organization of the 2013 Arctic Forum session as part of the the AGU Science Policy Conference, in Washington, D.C.
- **AGU Exploration Station** – Provided partial staff support and minor materials/shipping costs for an arctic and climate change educational booth at the annual AGU Exploration Station, a public outreach activity conducted prior to the AGU Fall Meeting. The event was free and open to members of the San Francisco public.
- **Extreme Cold Weather (ECW) Gear Kit** – Mailed ECW kits to teachers and the public as requested; teachers used the ECW kits (which includes a parka and similar cold weather gear) as a tool to teach about the polar regions.

*** What opportunities for training and professional development has the project provided?**

Opportunities for training and professional development included:

- Members of the ARCUS staff have been mentored on new skills, including budgeting processes, workshop planning and report development, and science planning and committee management.
- The ARCUS web developer attended a professional development conference on web database /content management software
- Two additional ARCUS staff attended a project management training course.
- The Research Support and Logistics Workshop provided opportunities for early career researchers to provide input to future directions of arctic logistics support.
- Activities at the AGU Fall meeting 2013 provides development development: ARCUS staff attend sessions to learn about arctic science and education developments; the ARCUS Community Meeting Room and associated Town Halls are venues for early career researchers to connect with established researchers.

*** How have the results been disseminated to communities of interest?**

The results of project activities are widely disseminated:

Website: The main method of dissemination is the ARCUS website at: <http://www.arcus.org/>. In 2013, the ARCUS website had 97,599 visits and 199,780 pageviews. In addition, the site serves 10,400 separate files (PDFs, PowerPoint files, etc.).

ArcticInfo Email List - Open mailing list that serves and the primary mailing list for sharing information on arctic science; there are over 6,800 email subscribers (<http://www.arcus.org/arctic-info>).

Witness the Arctic Newsletter - Many of ARCUS activities are reported in our online newsletter, Witness the Arctic, which has three issues a year (<http://www.arcus.org/witness-the-arctic>). The newsletter is distributed through a Witness the Arctic email list (with over 6,800 subscribers) as well as the ArcticInfo mailing list. Hardcopies of the newsletter were distributed at the 2013 Arctic Forum conference, the 2013 AGU Fall Meeting, and were requested by NSF Polar Programs information officer for distribution by NSF at the 2013 AGU Fall Meeting.

Twitter - In 2013, ARCUS started a twitter account with daily tweets about ARCUS activities and other news items of interest. There are currently 493 followers.

Conferences and Workshops - In 2013, information on ARCUS activities was distributed through various conference presentations (see the "Products" section in this report), and through flyers distributed through an Arctic Community Meeting Room at the 2013 AGU Fall Meeting, which drew over 400 people for various side meetings on arctic science topics.

Direct outreach and dissemination - including more focused email lists and groups (e.g., Sea Ice Outlook mailing list, Polar Education mailing list); through circulating draft reports and documents to relevant stakeholders, and contacting interested parties through email and phone.

Facebook - Facebook is utilized for specific projects, such as reaching Alaskan coastal communities for outreach of Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook reports.

*** What do you plan to do during the next reporting period to accomplish the goals?**

The next reporting period will be a short duration and will span from 1 January-30 April 2014, when the grant is ending. Many tasks will be winding down, but the planned activities include:

- Finalize the Research Support and Logistics Workshop Report.
- Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) - Finalize the transition between the current governance structure and new governance structure; all activities under the new structure will be funded through a separate grant.

- Support the IARPC Secretariat; complete the next phase of IARPC website development.
 - Arctic Observing Network: Continue management of AON Discussion Funding program
 - Publish and disseminate the Winter 2014 issue of Witness the Arctic
 - Launch the 2014 season of the Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook (SIWO); produce weekly reports through April.
 - Develop online communications, including that through ArcticInfo mailing list, the online Arctic Calendar, and the ARCUS website.
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Products

Books

Book Chapters

Conference Papers and Presentations

Inventions

Journals

Licenses

Other Products

Other Publications

Helen V Wiggins, Susan E. Fox, Betsy Turner-Bogren (2013). *Collaboration and the Science-Policy Nexus in Arctic Research*. Poster Presentation at the AGU Science Policy Conference 2013. Status = PUBLISHED; Acknowledgement of Federal Support = No

Eicken, H., Bitz, C.M., Gascard, J., Kaminski, T., Karcher, M.J., Kauker, F., Overland, J.E., Stroeve, J.C., Wiggins, H.V. (2013). *Creating collaboration opportunities for marine research across the Arctic: The SEARCH-ACCESS partnership and an emerging sea ice prediction research network*. Poster Presentation at Fall AGU Meeting. Status = PUBLISHED; Acknowledgement of Federal Support = Yes

Hajo Eicken, Olivia Lee, George Kling, Craig Lee, Helen Wiggins, and the SEARCH Science Steering Committee (2013). *Dual-purpose Arctic Observing networks: Lessons from SEARCH on frameworks for prioritization and coordination..* White paper for Arctic Observing Summit, Vancouver, BC, Canada, April 30-May 2013. Status = PUBLISHED; Acknowledgement of Federal Support = No

Helen Wiggins, Hajo Eicken, Susan E. Fox (2013). *SEARCH: Study of Environmental Arctic Change – A System-scale, Cross-disciplinary Arctic Research Program*. Poster presentation at the 2013 Alaska Marine Science Symposium. Status = PUBLISHED; Acknowledgement of Federal Support = Yes

SEARCH Science Steering Committee, Reija Shnorro, Hajo Eicken, Jennifer Francis, Ted Scambos, E.A.G. Schuur, Fiamma Straneo, Helen V. Wiggins (2013). *SEARCH: Study of Environmental Arctic Change—A System-scale, Cross-disciplinary Arctic Research Program*. Poster Presentation at AGU 2013 Fall Meeting. Status = PUBLISHED; Acknowledgement of Federal Support = Yes

Susan E. Fox and Helen V. Wiggins (2013). *The Arctic Research Consortium of the United States (ARCUS)*. Poster presentation at the 2013 Alaska Marine Science Symposium. Status = PUBLISHED; Acknowledgement of Federal Support = No

Wiggins, H. V., Fahnestock, J. (2013). *The Arctic Visiting Speakers Program*. Poster Presentation at the AGU Fall

2013 Meeting. Status = PUBLISHED; Acknowledgement of Federal Support = Yes

Payne, J., D. Perovich, R. Shnorro, and H. Wiggins, eds. (2013). *U.S. Arctic Observing Network Coordination Workshop Report*. Report from a workshop. Status = PUBLISHED; Acknowledgement of Federal Support = Yes

Patents

Technologies or Techniques

Thesis/Dissertations

Websites

ARCUS Website

<http://www.arcus.org/>

The main ARCUS website contains information on all task areas covered under this grant.

Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH)

<http://www.arcus.org/search-program>

Information on all SEARCH activities and structure, including meetings, publications, and other activities. Also includes the Sea Ice Outlook and Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook websites/webpages.

Participants/Organizations

What individuals have worked on the project?

Name	Most Senior Project Role	Nearest Person Month Worked
Wiggins, Helen	PD/PI	9

Full details of individuals who have worked on the project:

Helen V Wiggins

Email: helen@arcus.org

Most Senior Project Role: PD/PI

Nearest Person Month Worked: 9

Contribution to the Project: Principal Investigator of project; directs programs and activities for tasks under this grant.

Funding Support: N/a

International Collaboration: No

International Travel: No

What other organizations have been involved as partners?

Name	Type of Partner Organization	Location
Eskimo Walrus Commission	Other Nonprofits	Nome, AK

Name	Type of Partner Organization	Location
NOAA	Other Organizations (foreign or domestic)	Seattle, Washington
University of Alaska Fairbanks	Academic Institution	Fairbanks, Alaska
Webitects, Inc.	Industrial or Commercial Firms	Chicago

Full details of organizations that have been involved as partners:

Eskimo Walrus Commission

Organization Type: Other Nonprofits

Organization Location: Nome, AK

Partner's Contribution to the Project:

Other: Collaborative activities

More Detail on Partner and Contribution: ARCUS worked with the Eskimo Walrus Commission, who served as a partner/advisor on the Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook activity.

NOAA

Organization Type: Other Organizations (foreign or domestic)

Organization Location: Seattle, Washington

Partner's Contribution to the Project:

In-Kind Support

More Detail on Partner and Contribution: ARCUS worked with NOAA staff (Jim Overland) to develop monthly Sea Ice Outlook reports.

University of Alaska Fairbanks

Organization Type: Academic Institution

Organization Location: Fairbanks, Alaska

Partner's Contribution to the Project:

Other: Collaborative activities

More Detail on Partner and Contribution: ARCUS works with Hajo Eicken (UAF), SEARCH SSC Chair, on SEARCH activities.

Webitects, Inc.

Organization Type: Industrial or Commercial Firms

Organization Location: Chicago

Partner's Contribution to the Project:

Other: Collaborative contract work

More Detail on Partner and Contribution: ARCUS worked with Webitects on development of a website needs assessment

Have other collaborators or contacts been involved? Yes

Impacts**What is the impact on the development of the principal discipline(s) of the project?**

Since this is not a research project, activities are not focused on one discipline, per se. Activities have led to synthesis of knowledge across disciplines (such as through the Arctic Observing Coordination report, the Sea Ice Outlook, and the Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook). In addition, a suite of learned best practices and methodologies for collaboration and communication have been developed. Key of these are: 1) Identify the type of collaboration appropriate for your goals. 2) Identify key players. 3) Design a process for managing the collaboration. 4) Foster good relationships throughout, 5) Don't underestimate the support and resources needed, and 6) Be patient.

What is the impact on other disciplines?

Activities under this Cooperative Agreement have enhanced communication and transfer of information within and among scientists of many disciplines in the arctic (physical, natural, and social scientists), the public, and identified stakeholders. Activities such as workshops and online reports, and communications with the newsletter and email lists, are instrumental in sharing information between disciplines of arctic research.

What is the impact on the development of human resources?

Activities over the past year that have impacted the development of human resources include: the Arctic Visiting Speakers Series, which reaches thousands of members of the public each year; Alaskan coastal communities/Native Alaskans are reached through the Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook; the polar education email list, which provides information on polar science to educators; and travel support of early career scientists to workshop such as the Research Support and Logistics workshop.

What is the impact on physical resources that form infrastructure?

Nothing to report.

What is the impact on institutional resources that form infrastructure?

The project activities overall facilitate and support the health of ARCUS as a non-profit consortium of member institutions with interest in arctic research and/or education.

What is the impact on information resources that form infrastructure?

Nearly all of the activities funded under this grant have associated information resources. The ARCUS website provides information infrastructure that offers an array of resources and services from diverse sources; all of these resources are publicly accessible.

What is the impact on technology transfer?

Nothing to report.

What is the impact on society beyond science and technology?

ARCUS has made great strides in enabling the Arctic science community to connect and become more integrated in their efforts of working together and engaging the public about arctic science.

Changes/Problems**Changes in approach and reason for change**

Nothing to report.

Actual or Anticipated problems or delays and actions or plans to resolve them

Nothing to report.

Changes that have a significant impact on expenditures

Nothing to report.

Significant changes in use or care of human subjects

Nothing to report.

Significant changes in use or care of vertebrate animals

Nothing to report.

Significant changes in use or care of biohazards

Nothing to report.